

Comparison Of Metronome Speed in Step Exercise Training Against Harvard Step Test Duration

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Abstract

Being a member of the Medical Assistance Team requires not only excellent health but also optimal physical fitness, considering that Indonesia is a disaster-prone area where disasters can occur anytime and anywhere. Respondents were members of the Medical Assistance Team of the Medical Faculty of Medicine, Warmadewa University, which aimed to determine the comparison of the step exercise (SE) method on post-exercise heart rate and resting heart rate in TBM. This study used 71 respondents who were divided into 3 groups using a simple random method. Group P1 performed SE at a speed of 100 x / minute for 216 seconds, group P2 performed SE at a speed of 110 x / minute for 196 seconds, group P3 performed SE at a speed of 120 x / minute for 180 seconds, the exercise was carried out for 4 weeks (3 times per week). All respondents took the Harvard Step Test (HST) and compared the results before and after exercise. The results of the comparison of the three groups showed that group P2 was proven to be more effective and efficient in improving cardiorespiratory fitness as walking, running, cycling and other aerobic activities. The conclusion obtained is that SE training with a speed of 110 x/minute for 196 seconds using stairs (20 cm high) with moderate intensity and moderate duration can be a recommendation for effective and efficient aerobic exercise in improving cardiorespiratory fitness.

Keywords: step exercise speed and duration, Harvard step test duration, cardiorespiratory endurance

INTRODUCTION

Cardiorespiratory fitness, sometimes called aerobic capacity, refers to the ability of the cardiorespiratory system to supply oxygen to the muscles of the body during physical activity of varying intensity. Specifically, cardiorespiratory fitness is measured by the maximum oxygen volume (VO₂ max), which reflects the body's ability to utilize oxygen during maximal aerobic exercise. Optimal cardiorespiratory health is necessary to maintain good cardiovascular health, enhance endurance, and support daily physical activity. Recent research suggests that low cardiorespiratory fitness is associated with an increased risk of cardiovascular disease, obesity, and premature death (1). In recent years, our understanding of the factors that influence cardiorespiratory fitness has advanced significantly. Genetic, environmental, lifestyle, and dietary and exercise factors have all been shown to play a significant role in determining a person's

cardiorespiratory fitness level (2). In addition, research has highlighted the importance of behavioral interventions and appropriate exercise programs in improving cardiorespiratory fitness and reducing the risk of cardiovascular disease (3). Aerobic exercise is one method that has been shown to be effective in improving cardiorespiratory fitness, except in very severe cases where improvement is unlikely without surgery or other medical intervention. Aerobic exercise can range from as simple as walking or climbing stairs, to as strenuous as running a marathon. Aerobic exercise can generally be done indoors and outdoors, either individually or in groups. Aerobic exercise methods vary greatly in duration, intensity, and frequency of exercise, using aids such as bicycles, treadmills, box step exercises, rowing machines and without aids (7), (8).

Various methods have been proven relevant in measuring cardiopulmonary fitness, both using sophisticated equipment such as measuring maximum oxygen volume (VO₂Max), running tests, both using distance (1 mile runs test) and using time (12-minute

runs test), stair climbing tests such as the Harvard Step Test and YMCA Step Test which measure duration and heart rate as parameters of the test (9).

The Baswara Prada Medical Assistance Team (TBM) is a student organization engaged in the field of medical emergencies under the auspices of the Student Executive Board-Student Institution of the Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, Warmadewa University (BEM-LM FKIK UNWAR). As members of the Baswara Prada TBM, students are required to have basic medical assistance competencies and also have excellent physical fitness considering that emergencies can occur anywhere and in varying terrain conditions from light to extremely heavy (10).

One of the physical fitness that must be possessed by members of the Baswara Prada TBM is cardiorespiratory endurance or cardiopulmonary endurance. One of the tests to measure cardiopulmonary endurance fitness for members of the Baswara Prada TBM is the Harvard Step Test (HST), where the duration of the HST and the recovery pulse are parameters that determine the level of fitness for the test. Research conducted by Artha, Subrata and Kerans in 2023 showed that the Harvard Step Test Ability Index was 40% of students in the very poor category, 27.1% in the poor category, 27.1% in the sufficient category, only 5.7% in the good category and no students in the very good category. From the duration of the test, it was found that the average test could be done in 93.51 seconds from the target of 300 seconds. This study aims to determine the comparison of metronome speed/beat in effective step exercise training to increase the duration of HST which will have an impact on increasing the Harvard Step Test Ability Index. This study uses an experimental research approach with a pre-test and post-test group design, which is divided into 3 treatment groups, with

modifications to the metronome speed/beat in step exercise training. This study is expected to provide new insights into effective training methods in improving cardiopulmonary fitness for TBM students and the wider community (11).

METHOD

This study employed an experimental research design with a pre-test and post-test setup, divided into three treatment groups. It was conducted over a period of six months, from January to May 2023, at the Faculty of Medicine, University of Warmadewa. The study population consisted of all members of TBM Baswara Prada. The sample included members of TBM Baswara Prada who met the inclusion criteria, which specified male and female participants aged 19-21 who were willing to participate. Participants were selected through a simple random sampling method. Based on sample size calculations, a minimum of 71 participants was required.

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Research and Development Unit University of Warmadewa, Denpasar, with ethical clearance under the reference number 323 / Unwar / FKIK / EC-KEPK / IV / 2023. The collected data were analyzed descriptively, with the results presented in the form of frequencies, percentages, and graphs. To assess the correlation between metronome speed/beat in step exercise training and the duration of the Harvard Step Test (HST), a paired t-test was used if the data were normally distributed, or the Wilcoxon test if the data were not normally distributed. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Research Procedure

The research subjects were assembled to receive instructions and technical details regarding the data collection process to be conducted.

The research subjects then provided basic respondent information prior to the measurements, in order to confirm inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Cardiorespiratory endurance was assessed

using the Harvard Step Test. The procedure began by setting up a bench with a height of 47.5 centimeters for men and 40 centimeters for women. A metronome was adjusted to a pace of 120 beats per minute. The subject then stepped up and down on the bench for a maximum of 5 minutes (300 seconds) or until they could no longer maintain the metronome's rhythm. After completing the test, the subject sat down to rest for 1 minute, and their recovery pulse was measured for 30 seconds.

Harvard Step Test Assessment

Formula = Time (duration of test in seconds) X 100: 5.5 X number of recovery pulses. Harvard Step Test Ability Index Category:

1. Very good ability: 90
2. Good ability: 80-89
3. Fair ability: 65-79
4. Moderate ability: 55-64
5. Poor ability: >54

Subjects were randomly assigned to three groups: P1, P2, and a control group (P3), all of which used 20 cm high stairs. Group P1 performed step test exercises at a speed of 100 beats per minute for 216 seconds (3 minutes and 36 seconds), three times a week for 4 weeks. Group P2 conducted the step test at a speed of 110 beats per minute for 196 seconds (3 minutes and 16 seconds), also three times a week for 4 weeks. The control group (P3) did the step test at a speed of 120 beats per minute for 180 seconds (3 minutes), following the same frequency of three times a week for 4 weeks. After completing the 4 weeks of exercise, all subjects underwent the Harvard Step Test again to compare the duration of the HST across the three groups. Once all subject data and measurement results were collected, the data will be analyzed.

RESULT

A normality test using the Shapiro-Wilk test was conducted for the three

groups. The results showed that most of the p-values were greater than 0.05, indicating that the data followed a normal distribution. Consequently, the paired sample t-test was applied for further analysis. In group P1, the pre-P1 duration normality test resulted in a p-value of 0.052, and the post-P1 test yielded a p-value of 0.549. Since both p-values were greater than 0.05, the data were considered normally distributed, and the paired sample t-test was used for the next step.

The duration of the test in pre-P1 obtained an average HST duration of 96.45 ± 48.23 and post-P1 obtained an average HST duration of 180.409 ± 38.73 . From the comparison of pre- and post-P1 with the paired T test, the results of the HST duration pre-post p value > 0.05 ($0.00 < 0.05$) there is a relationship or influence with the HST duration variable (H 1 is accepted H0 is rejected). In group P2, the results of the pre-P2 duration normality test were 0.122 and post-P2 0.055, the results of the normality test showed a p value > 0.05 , so the data distribution was normal, the next test was the paired sample T test. The duration of the test in pre-P2 obtained an average HST duration of 93.72 ± 39.31 and post-P2 obtained an average HST duration of 193.520 ± 40.52 . From the comparison of pre- and post-P2 with the paired T test, the results of the HST duration pre - post p value > 0.05 ($0.00 < 0.05$) there is a relationship or influence with the HST duration variable (H 1 accepted H0 rejected) In group P3, the results of the pre-P3 duration normality test were 0.06 and post-P3 0.351, the results of the normality test showed a p value > 0.05 , so the data distribution was normal, the next test was the paired sample T test. The test duration at pre P3 obtained an average HST duration of 90.37 ± 40.49 and post P3 obtained an average HST duration of 186.84 ± 40.794 .

From the comparison of pre and post P2 with the paired T test, the results of the HST duration pre - post p value > 0.05 ($0.00 < 0.05$) there is a relationship or influence with the HST duration variable (H 1 is accepted H0 is rejected).

Table 1. Durasi HST P1, P2, P3

Resting Pulse	N	Mean ± SD Pre	Mean ± SD Post	Mean ± SD Selisih Pre-Post	95% CI of the Difference		t	Sig. (2-tailed)
					Lower	Upper		
P1	22	96.4545± 48.22638	180.4091± 38.72696	-83.95455± 40.63950	- 101.973	- -65.936	- 9.690	0.000
P2	25	93.720± 39.30598	193.520± 40.52275	-99.80000± 39.93641	- 116.284	- 83.3150	- 12.495	0.000
P3	19	90.3684± 40.49171	186.8421± 40.79388	-96.47368± 42.55894	- 116.986	- 75.9609	- -9.881	0.000

DISCUSSION

A similar study by Subrata *et al* demonstrated that the step exercise method significantly reduced resting heart rate and recovery heart rate, which indirectly indicates an improvement in cardiorespiratory fitness (12). Step Exercise training can be carried out in easy places with simple procedures (benches, stairs, and steps), in contrast to walking and running training which tend to require wider locations and require more specific and expensive equipment (static bicycles or treadmills) (13).

The theory of biomechanics, aerobic exercise such as walking uses some of the large leg muscles (gluteus, quadriceps, biceps femoris, gastrocnemius, and soleus) in a small-scale range of motion (ROM). Other exercises such as running involve some of the same muscles but with a larger scale ROM and higher capacity. Unlike SE training which only uses large leg muscles but with a larger scale ROM than running training, especially in the quadriceps femoris, gluteus, gastrocnemius, and biceps femoris muscles with a combination of capacity with a more innovative intensity than just running training (14). If the intensity of running capacity can be modified by increasing speed and elevation, then high-intensity SE training can add some of the stride length, bench height, and rhythm. So that it is able to increase upper body movement activity (15), (16). The results of research from Scharff-Olson *et. al*. proves that the main factors that affect SE training are; speed in training, forced step maneuver movement, selected step height and additional load weight increase. This study

also concluded that ground reaction forces (GRF) when performing step movements on stairs tend to be lower than when running related to the direct relationship of movement with step height and types of exercise with maneuver movement (17). The results of the review of the study showed that in tests using various SE methods, the bench height values used for SE were 15.2 cm (6 inches, B-6), 20.3 cm (8 inches, B-8), 25.4 cm (10 inches, B-10), and 30.5 cm (12 inches, B-12), it was found that the higher the bench used in SE training, the better the impact of the response of lung function capacity, namely VO₂max, which was measured and experienced a significant increase (18).

In this research study, the results of the modification to measure the intensity and duration given to SE training, obtained results from P1 with low intensity with a long duration (speed of 100 beats per minute for 216 seconds), while P2 showed results with moderate intensity with a moderate duration (speed of 110 beats per minute for 196 seconds) and finally the results of P3 showed a high intensity value with a faster duration (speed of 120 beats per minute for 180 seconds (based on the speed value on the Harvard Step Test). From these results, it proves that there is a difference in the pre and post averages which shows that moderate intensity SE with a moderate duration produces an increase in cardiorespiratory fitness that is comparable to activities such as walking, running, and cycling. Unlike other physical activities, SE training does not require complex and special materials and equipment such as treadmills, stationary bikes, or bicycles, nor does it

require a special place such as a jogging track or bike path. Meanwhile, the opposite effect was found by the results of a study by Permadi et.al who (2021) studied the effectiveness of low-intensity versus high-intensity aerobic exercise combined with aerobic exercise in the form of a treadmill and stationary bicycle in patients with a history of post-Covid-19, the results showed that the combination of aerobic exercise was more effective in increasing the capacity of cardiorespiratory function than aerobic exercise with only one exercise method (21). In another study conducted by Regnaud *et. al.* which compared physical activity or high-intensity versus low-intensity exercise in people with hip or knee osteoarthritis, proved that there was no significant difference between high-intensity and low-intensity exercise (22). It is therefore suggested that high intensity exercise programs may have more harmful and undesirable effects than lower intensity exercise programs (21), (23), (24).

CONCLUSION

Step Exercise training has been shown to be an effective and efficient method for improving cardiorespiratory fitness, comparable to activities like walking, running, and cycling. Unlike these activities, SE training doesn't require specialized equipment such as treadmills, stationary bikes, or bicycles, nor does it need designated spaces like jogging tracks or bike paths. The use of a 20 cm step height, which corresponds to the standard height of most stairs, makes it accessible and easy to practice. Studies have demonstrated that P1, P2, and P3 SE training significantly increase the average HST duration, with P2 showing the most significant increase. The duration of HST is an important parameter in the Harvard Step Test Ability Index, with longer HST duration indicating a better Harvard Step Test Ability Index score.

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